

The Analysis of Idiomatic Expression in Bidirectional Texts of Children Stories “Ceritarakyat Bali” and “the Little Mermaid”: an Introduction of Idiomatic Expression to Children

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Abstract: English can also be learnt from childhood. In learning English the children can read the bilingual stories. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (1995)--bilingual story is a story which are expressed or written in two languages, BI-directional book stories (English-Indonesian; Indonesian-English) are very interesting ways for children in learning English and Indonesian. In the children stories, there are numerous of idiomatic expression, which are found, in this case it is very interesting to introduce the idiomatic expression to children in order to enrich their knowledge about language, thus this study will be conducted to explore the translation strategies of the translator in translating the idioms in the BI-directional children stories in order to be understood easier by the children as the target reader. Since in the stories entitled “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The little Mermaid” show numerous idiomatic expressions which are needed as the data to be analyzed, so they are chosen as the data source.

Keywords: Translation, idiomatic expression, children story

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In translation there are so many theories and procedures that should be concerned by the translator. The purpose is to transfer the message from the source language to the target language and the message that they want to convey must be acceptable to the readers. Susanthi (2020: 91) stated that translation is getting more and more important nowadays, because most of the texts are in foreign languages, especially English as an International language which is mostly spoken by the people to communicate all over the world. In Indonesia, English can be as the second language, or third language, it is as the second language when they speak Indonesian as the first language and English as the second language that is usually learnt at school, or it is also found that some Indonesian speak local language, national language (Indonesian) and they learn English at their school as their third language.

Susanthi (2019: 1) states that English can also be learnt from childhood. In learning English the children can read the bilingual stories. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (1995)--bilingual story is a story which are expressed or written in two languages, BI-directional book stories (English-Indonesian; Indonesian-English) are very interesting ways for children in learning English and Indonesian. In the children stories, there are numerous of idiomatic expression, which are found, in this case it is very interesting to introduce the idiomatic expression to children in order to enrich their knowledge about language, thus this study will be conducted to explore the translation strategies of the translator in translating the idioms in the BI-directional children stories in order to be understood easier by the children as the target reader. Since in the stories entitled “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The little Mermaid” show numerous idiomatic expressions which are needed as the data to be analyzed, so they are chosen as the data source.

Based on the explanation above, this research will help the people especially children to understand about idiomatic expression both in Indonesian and English, thus this research is important to be conducted.

1.2 The Problems of the Study

Based on the explanation above, there are some problems which could turn up in this study. This study will present these following problems:

1. What types of idiomatic expression are found in BI-directional texts “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The Little Mermaid” and what are their equivalent to the TL?
2. What kinds of strategies used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression?
3. Why the strategies are chosen by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression and are the strategies properly used by the translator?

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study is mainly divided into two: general objective and specific objective. Each of them will be explaining in the following:

1.3.1 General Objectives

1. To give more contributions to the references of translation works
2. To enrich our perspective on the process of translating the idiom especially relating to the children as the target readers

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To identify the types of idiomatic expression in the bi-directional texts of children stories “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The Little Marmaid” and to find out their equivalent translation to the TL
2. To find out the strategies used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression
3. To find out whether the strategies properly used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression relating them to the children as the target reader

1.4 The Significance of the Study

The significance of this study which should be concerned are:

1. This study has positive contribution to the development of translation, as the part of linguistic studies
2. It is considered significant particularly in the production of translation of idiomatic expressions in BI-directional texts especially relating them to the children as the target reader. This reason is still having less concern of students to enrich the world of translation references.

1.5 The Scope of the Study

The focus of this study is on the BI-directional children stories (English-Indonesian and Indonesian-English translation) entitled “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The Little Mermaid” . Certainly the analysis just focuses on the translation process of the idiomatic expression. The discussion of the study will cover:

1. The identification of the idiomatic expressions in BI-directional children stories entitled “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The Little Mermaid” and to find out their equivalent translation to the TL

2. To find out the strategies used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression.
3. To find out whether the strategies properly used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression relating them to the children as the target reader

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE, CONCEPTS AND THE RHETORICAL FRAME WORK

2.1 Review of Literature

There are several books and articles which are relevant to the field of the idiomatic translation. They are:

Sudrama (2003) writes about *The Strategies Applied for Translating English Metaphor into Indonesian*. In his paper, Sudrama quotes some statements of different experts about idiom and metaphor.

Pastini (2004) Analyzes *The Translation Equivalence of English Noun Phrase*, she states that the equivalence in translation through the use of translation procedures, and translation is done to find the closest equivalence from SL to TL.

Karamanian (2002) in her article *Translation and Culture*, states that translation is not just dealing with words written in a certain time, space and sociopolitical situation; most importantly it is the “cultural” aspect of the text that should be taken into account. The process of transfer, i.e., re-coding across cultures, should consequently allocate corresponding attributes vis-a-vis the target culture to ensure credibility in the eyes of target reader.

2.2 Concepts

This study is based on the ideas proposed by some experts in the field of translation studies. The concepts which are used in this study are:

Mc Arthur (1992:402) states that figurative language is language in which figures of speech such as metaphors and similes freely occurs. He also explains that figures of speech as a rhetorical device that achieve a special effect by using words in distinctive ways, idiom proposed by Larson (1990) and Palmer (1981).

Larson (1990: 121) presents some types of figures speech. They are:

Antithesis: A figure of speech, in which sharply contrasting ideas, is juxtaposed in a balanced or parallel phrase or grammatical structure, euphemism: The act or an example of substituting a mild, indirect, or vague term for one considered harsh, blunt or offensive, hyperbole: A figure of speech in which exaggeration is used for emphasizing or effect, irony: The use of words to express something different from and often opposite to their literal meaning, metaphor: A figure of speech in which a word or phrase that ordinarily designates one thing is used to designate on other, thus making an implicit comparison, metonymy: A figure of speech, in which one word or phrase is substituted for another with which, it is closely associated. Paradox: The statement that seems to be absurd or contradictory but is or may be true, personification: The presentation of an object or concept as if it were a person, Pleonasm: The use of more words than is necessary to express the meaning, Sarcasm: The use of bitter, especially ironic, remarks intended to wound somebody's feelings, Simile: A figure of speech in which two essentially unlike things are compared, often in a phrase introduced by “like” or “as”, Synecdoche: A figure of speech in which a part is used for the whole, the whole for a part, the specific for the general, the general for the specific, material for the thing from which it is made and Idiom.

2.2.2 Expression

Kamus Bahasa Indonesia (Purwodarminta, 1976: 1129) explains that expression is a particular words, which conveys meaning through figurative speech (short sentences, a group of words, and phrases).

2.2.3. Idiom

Some linguist propose the definition of idiom. Larson (1998: 125) : idioms are expressions of at least two words which can not be understood literally and which function as a unit semantically. Palmer (1981:36) : idiom is a sequence of words whose meaning cannot be predicted from the meanings of the words themselves. Palmer (1981:80) proposes some types of idiom. They are:

Phrasal Verb : is the idiom consisting of the combination of verb plus adverb, such as *look after*, *goup* and sequences of verb, adverb and preposition as well, such as *put up with* (tolerate), or *do away with* (kill)

Partial Idiom: is idiom where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequences.

2.2.4 Idiomatic Expression

In Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (1995: 589), idiom is a phrase or sentence whose meaning is not clear from the meaning of its individual words and which must be learnt as a whole unit.

In Merriam-Webster's collegiate Dictionary (2003: 616), idiom is an expression in the usage of a language that is peculiar to itself either grammatically (as, No, it wasn't me) or in having a meaning that cannot be divided from conjoined meanings of its elements.

From the explanation above it can be understood that the idiom is the part of expression. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (1995:589) strengthens all these statement by giving definition that Idiomatic--using or containing expressions that are natural to a native speaker of a language. Idiomatic contains an idiom or idioms--an idiomatic expression/language.

Idiomatic expression is a particular word, phrase or sentence containing idiom

2.2.5 Equivalence

Equivalence proposed by Catford (1978), Nida (1964) and Baker (1991)

Cartford (1978: 20): equivalence is one of the aspects that should be well organized in translating the SL text into TL text. Equivalence is taken to be the basis on which source language (SL) textual material is replaced by target language (TL) textual material. Nida (1964:159) proposed formal and dynamic equivalence.

Formal equivalence: Focuses attention on the message itself, in both form and content. Dynamic equivalence: is based on the principle of equivalent effect. The concern of this translation is not to the matching of receptor-language message with the source language message, but with dynamic relationship

Baker (1992) explores the notion of equivalence at different levels, in relation to translation process, including all different aspects of translation. She distinguishes between:

Equivalence at word level: When the translator start analyzing SL s/he looks at the words as single units in order to find a direct equivalent term in the TL

Grammatical Equivalence: grammatical rules may vary across languages and this may pose problems in terms of finding a direct correspondence in the TL

Textual Equivalence: when referring to the equivalence between a SL text and a TL text in terms of information and cohesion. The translator will be guided by three main factors: the target audience, the purpose of the translation and the text type.

Pragmatic Equivalence: The translator needs to work out implied meanings in translation in order to get the SL message across. The role of the translator is to recreate the author's intention in another culture in such a way that enables the reader to understand it clearly.

2.2.6 Meaning

Leech (1977: 10) presents meaning in seven types:

III. Conceptual meaning, Connotative meaning, Stylistic meaning, Affective meaning, Reflective meaning, Collocative meaning, Thematic meaning.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Translation

The theory that will be used in this study is mainly the theory of translation proposed by Larson (1998). To support the discussion, some other translation theories proposed by Baker, and Venuti will be presented in this discussion.

Larson (1998): translation involves the transfer of form and meaning of the source language to the target language. A translator will often find that there is no exact equivalent between the languages. Larson also states that translation is a process which begins with source text, analyzes this text into semantic structure and then restructure this semantic structure into appropriate reception language forms in order to create an equivalent reception language text. He also states that translation consists of transferring the meaning of the source language into the receptor language. There are three kinds of meaning. They are referential, organizational, and situational (contextual) meaning. The translation goal is to reproduce the receptor language text that communicates the same messages as in the source language by using the natural expressions in the receptor language. His goal is an idiomatic translation. Larson (1998:19) states that the idiomatic translation is reproducing the meaning of the source language (the meaning intended by the original communicator) in the natural form in the receptor language. And in order to translate idiomatically, a translator will need to make many adjustments in form.

2.3.2 Translation Procedure

Vinay and Darbellnet (in Venuti, 2000: 84) state that a translator may choose one of the methods in doing translation. There are seven procedures. The first three procedures are direct and the rest are oblique. They are: Borrowing, Calque, Literal translation, Transposition, Modulation, Equivalence and Adaptation.

2.3.3 The Types of Idioms Adjustment

Nida and Taber (1974:106) propose the types of Idioms Adjustment:

- From idioms to non idiom
- From idioms to idioms
- From non-idioms to idioms

2.3.4 Strategies in Translating Idioms

Above word level, Baker (1992:70) stated four strategies in translating idioms, namely:

using an idiom of similar meaning and form: this strategy involves using an idiom in the TL which conveys roughly the same meaning as that of the SL idiom and, in addition, consists of equivalent lexical item.

Using an idiom of similar meaning but dissimilar Form: it is often possible to find an idiom or fixed expression in the TL which has a meaning similar to that of the source idiom or expression, but which consists of different lexical items.

Translation by Paraphrase: This is by far the most common way of translating idioms when a match cannot be found in the TL or when it seems inappropriate to use idiomatic language in the TL because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

Translation by Omission: This strategy may sound rather drastic, but in fact it does not harm to omit translating a word or expression in some context.

IV. METHOD OF RESEARCH

3.1 Data Source

In defining the data source of this study, the theory of parallel corpora proposed by Olohan (2004) is used. Olohan (2004: 24) states that Parallel corpora can be:

unidirectional I.e., source texts in language A and target texts in language B

Bidirectional, I.e. source texts in language A and translations in language B, and source texts in language B and their translations in language A. The bi-directional texts entitled “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The Little Mermaid” are chosen as the data to be analyzed.

The BI-directional texts is chosen--they can show numerous idiomatic expression; reading BI-directional texts as is one ways of bilingual speaker (English speaker who learns Indonesian and Indonesian speaker who learn English) in learning idiomatic expression of English and Indonesian, thus they can enrich the children knowledge.

3.2 Method and Technique of Data Collection

In collecting the data, the method proposed by Olohan (2004) is used. The data of this study was collected through library research. The data was taken from written materials based on printed-out texts. In the process of observing, the writer reads the BI-directional texts then makes identification. The samples of texts which are predicted as idiomatic translation are selected based on the concept which has been proposed. Those texts which consist of idiomatic expression are chosen for the sake of the aim of the research. The idiomatic expression are analyzed based on the theory which has been proposed.

3.3 Method and Technique of Analyzing Data

The method and technique of analyzing data is conducted by using qualitative method as proposed by Olohan (2004). Data which have been collected were classified into classification of problems. Both data of SL and TL are put one after another to make it easier to conduct the analysis. The Analysis of the BI-directional texts were presented into different sub-discussion. First, The data were grammatically analyzed to get the idea of how they are constructed. Analyzing them semantically to find out the idea of what semantic aspects are involved in the data analysis. Analyzing the idiomatic expressions and their equivalent in TL based on the theory which have been proposed consulting with kamus idiom and kamus Bahasa Indonesia to support the analysis. Analyzing the strategies used by the translator in translating idiomatic expression.

3.4 Method and Technique of Presenting Data Analysis

Concerning the data analysis is conducted by applying qualitative method, the analysis of data which are the idiomatic expression of SL and TL, can be figured out in the following example:

A. The Analysis of Idiomatic Expression English -Indonesian Translation

– SL: Although her father warned her never to go there, Ariel disobeyed him and went up to the surface quite often

– TL: Meskipun ayahnya telah memperingatkannya agar tidak kesana, Ariel mengabaikannya. Dia sering berenang ke permukaan laut

To analyze further the idiomatic expressions in both SL and TL such as the above examples, the writer will also analyze them into idiomatic analysis and the analysis of translation. “The Theory of Translation” by Nida and “Translation Procedure” by Vinay and Darbelet are used. Mean while in analyzing the strategies of translating idiomatic expression the theory proposed by Baker is used.

Analysis:

Went up is considered as the idiomatic expression of SL, it can be considered as an idiomatic expression since it can not be translated literally or word for word, because it will be meaningless. If it is translated literally into TL equivalent, the meaning is *is pergilikeatas*. The literal meanings cannot be accepted both in SL text and TL text because they really do not make sense. The phrase is categorized into idiomatic expression, because the expression cannot be identified literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. Since the target reader are the children. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression, so it is hoped this will be understood easier by the target audience. The phrase of the idiomatic expression is constructed from the combination of Verb + Preposition, thus it can be categorized as “phrasal idiomatic expression”. In translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by paraphrase, because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

B. The Analysis of Idiomatic Expression Indonesian-English Translation

– SL: Rupanya dia sudah mencarinya kemana-mana. Maklum Monyet dan Penyu adalah sahabat kental

– TL: Monkey had been looking for Turtle everywhere, since they were very good friends

Analysis:

The idiomatic expression of the examples above and its English Equivalent are *sahabat kental*--*Good Friends*. The phrase cannot be translated literally. The verb phrase would be meaningful if it is translated as unit semantically, thus it can be categorized as idiomatic expression. This idiomatic expression is categorized as partial idiomatic expression where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence. *Kental* refers to *not liquid*, but no *best friend* that are *not liquid*. Thus it does not make sense if it is translated literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. Since the target reader are the children. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression, so it is hoped this will be understood easier by the target audience. In translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by paraphrase, because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

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V. THE ANALYSIS OF IDIOMATIC BIDIRECTIONAL TEXTS OF CHILDREN STORIES

This chapter deals with the analysis of idiomatic expression as the main concern of this study. The objectives of this study are:

To identify the types of idiomatic expression in the BI-directional texts of children stories “Cerita Rakyat Bali” and “The Little Mermaid” and to find out their equivalent translation to the TL; To find out the strategies used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression; To find out whether the strategies properly used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression relating them to the children as the target reader.

The analysis of the data is mainly based on some theories such as:

“The theory of translation” proposed by Larson, “Translation Procedures” proposed by Vinay and Darbelnet, “Theory of the strategies in translating idioms” proposed by Baker.

The data found are presented by pairing up both of the idiomatic expressions of the SL and their equivalent in the TL. The process will be carried out into:

The types of idiomatic expression; The kinds of strategies used by translator in translating the idiomatic expression; The identification whether the strategies properly used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression relating them to the children as the target reader.

4.1 The Idiomatic expression in BI-directional Children stories

In this part of discussion, the writer presents the types of idiomatic expression, which have been identified in the BI-directional children stories. Bi-directional, i.e. source texts in language A and translations in language B, and source texts in language B and their translations in language A. The data of BI-directional used in this study are texts in English and translation in Indonesian, and texts in Indonesian and their translation in English. The analysis of idiomatic expression in BI-directional will be presented one after another into sub discussion.

4.1.1 The Idiomatic expressions in English texts and their translation in Indonesian

Data Example 1

– SL: He was worried about his daughter’s safety, and so he asked his trusted friend Sebastian the crab to keep an eye on Ariel

– TL: Dia mencemaskan keselamatan Ariel. Maka dia meminta sahabat kepercayaannya, Sebastian si kepiting, untuk mengawasi Ariel.

Analysis:

The phrase which is underlined *to keep an eye on* is considered as the idiomatic expression of SL, it can be considered as an idiomatic expression since it can not be translated literally or word for word, because it will be meaningless. If it is translated literally into TL equivalent, the meaning is *menetapkan sebuah mata*. Thus the literally translation will be meaningless. The phrase is categorized into idiomatic expression, because the expression cannot be identified literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. Consulting with Kamus Idiom the equivalent meaning of the phrase *to keep an eye on* is *mengawasi; memperhatikan*. Since the target reader are the children. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression. Moreover In translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by paraphrase, because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL, this strategy are chosen relating to the the children as the target audience, so the idiomatic expression can be

understood easier. The phrase of the idiomatic expression is constructed from the combination of Verb + Preposition, thus it can be categorized as “phrasal idiomatic expression”.

Data Example 2

– SL : Although her father warned her never to go there, Ariel disobeyed him and went up to the surface quite often

– TL : Meskipun ayahnya telah memperingatkannya agar tidak kesana, Ariel mengabaikannya. Dia sering berenang ke permukaan laut.

Analysis:

Went up is considered as the idiomatic expression of SL, it can be considered as an idiomatic expression since it cannot be translated literally or word for word, because it will be meaningless. If it is translated literally into TL equivalent, the meaning is *pergikeatas*. The literal meanings cannot be accepted both in SL text and TL text because they really do not make sense. The phrase is categorized into idiomatic expression, because the expression cannot be identified literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. Since the target reader are the children. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression, so it is hoped this will be understood easier by the target audience. The phrase of the idiomatic expression is constructed from the combination of Verb + Preposition, thus it can be categorized as “phrasal idiomatic expression”. In translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by paraphrase, because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

Data Example 3

– SL: King Triton was furious when he discovered that Ariel had fallen in love with a human

– TL: Raja Triton marah sekali, ketika dia tahu bahwa Ariel telah jatuh cinta pada seorang manusia

Analysis:

The idiomatic expression of the examples above and its English Equivalent are *fallen in love with--jatuh cinta pada*. The verb phrase would be meaningful if it is translated as unit semantically, thus it can be categorized as idiomatic expression. This idiomatic expression is categorized as partial idiomatic expression where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence. Love cannot be fallen. Thus, it will be meaningless if it is not translated as unit semantically. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to idiom. In translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by using an idiom of similar meaning and form. Consulting with Kamus Idiom the equivalent meaning of the phrase *fallen in love with this jatuh cinta*. The strategy of using an idiom of similar meaning or form is used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression because of the same stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

Data Example 4

– SL: If you can get him kiss you before the sun goes down on the third day, you will stay with him forever, as a human

– TL: Jika kau bisa membuatnya menciummu sebelum matahari terbenam pada hari ketiga, kau akan bersamanya selamanya, sebagai manusia.

Analysis:

The phrase which is underlined in the data 4, *thesungoesdown* is considered as the idiomatic expression of SL, the phrase *thesungoesdown* cannot be translated literally or word for word, because it will be meaningless. If it is translated literally into TL equivalent, the meaning will be *mataharipergiturun*. This can be considered meaningless. The expression cannot be identified literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. Consulting with Kamus Idiom the equivalent meaning of the phrase *godown istenggelum, thesungoesdown--mataharitenggelum*. In terms of the type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent the translator chooses the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression. Since the target reader are the children so the translator chooses this type of adjustment. This idiomatic expression is categorized as partial idiomatic expression where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence. The common term for *thesungoesdown* is *sunsets*. Thus, it will be meaningless if it is not translated as unit semantically.

Data example 5

- SL : Poor Ariel was heartbroken
- TL: Ariel patah hati

Analysis:

Since the verb phrase *Heartbroken* would be meaningful if it is translated as unit semantically, thus it can be categorized as idiomatic expression, moreover the expression cannot be identified literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. This idiomatic expression is categorized as partial idiomatic expression where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence. Heart cannot be broken if it is not translated as unit semantically. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to idiom. The strategy of using an idiom of similar meaning or form is used by the translator in translating the idiomatic expression because of the same stylistic preferences of the SL and TL. Consulting with Kamus Idiom the equivalent meaning of the phrase *heartbroken* is *patah hati*.

4.1.1 The Idiomatic expressions in Indonesian texts and their translation in English

Data Example 1

-SL: Rupanya dia sudah mencarinya kemana-mana. Maklum Monyet dan Penyu adalah sahabat kental

-TL: Monkey had been looking for Turtle everywhere, since they were very good friends

Analysis

The idiomatic expression of the examples above and its English Equivalent are *sahabat kental--Good Friends*. The phrase cannot be translated literally. The verb phrase would be meaningful if it is translated as unit semantically, thus it can be categorized as idiomatic expression. This idiomatic expression is categorized as partial idiomatic expression where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence. *Kental* refers to *not liquid*, but *no best friend* that *are not liquid*. Thus it does not make sense if it is translated literally but its meaning has been unity and it is specific. Since the target reader are the children. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression, so it is hoped this will be understood easier by the target audience. In translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by paraphrase, because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

Data Example 2

- SL: Denganakalnya yang busuksi Grantang oleh kakanya si Cupak disuruh untuk memerangi musuh negara berupa raksasa yang sakti.
- TL: Cupak, with his usual evil intentions, ordered his brother to go and attack their country's enemy, a giant with supernatural powers.

Analysis:

Since the phrase *akalnya yang busuk* would be meaningful if it is translated as unit semantically, thus it can be categorized as idiomatic expression. This idiomatic expression is categorized as partial idiomatic expression where one of the words has its usual meaning, the other has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence. *Busuk* refers to *rotten*, but no *intentions* which are *rotten*. Thus it does not make sense if it is not translated as unit semantically. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression, so it is hoped this will be understood easier by the target audience, because the target reader are the children, because of different stylistic preferences of the SL and TL so in translating the idiomatic expression from SL to TL, the translator uses the translation by paraphrase.

V

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

•5.1 Conclusion

There are both of phrasal and partial idiomatic expressions found in English Indonesian texts. Meanwhile there are only partial idiomatic expressions which are found in Indonesian-English texts. Since the target reader are the children. The type of adjustment in translating the SL idiomatic expression into TL equivalent which are mostly used by the translator is the type of translating from idiom to non-idiomatic expression, so it is hoped this will be understood easier by the target audience, except there is the same stylistic preferences of the SL and TL.

5.2 Suggestion

Translation plays a significance role in transferring knowledge, most of the knowledge books are in English. The knowledge itself not only for the adults but also for the children, thus here the translator play an important rule in transferring the message of SL to TL based on the target readers. So the target reader can accept the message easier

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